

Abstract No. 11

Evaluation of Pre-Emergence Herbicide to Control Weeds in Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

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Abstract The experiment was conducted at the research field of Bangladesh Wheat and Maize Research Institute, Nashipur, Dinajpur during Rabi season of 2023–24 and 2024–25. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The unit plot size was 4m × 4m and the variety was BWMRI Gom 3. Seeds were sown on 26 November, 2023 and 04 December, 2024 with a spacing of 20 cm apart from rows followed by continuous seeding. Eight different treatments were employed in this study viz. 1) Panida® 33 EC @ 2.5 L ha⁻¹, 2) Fist® 33 EC @ 3.0 L ha⁻¹, 3) Clear Up® 33 EC @ 2.5 L ha⁻¹, 4) Pendulam® 33 EC @ 2.0 L ha⁻¹, 5) Dafa® 33 EC @ 1.0 L ha⁻¹, 6) Kri Stop® 33 EC @ 2.0 L ha⁻¹, 7) Hand weeding at 25 DAS, 8) Weedy check (Control). Among the weed species *Scroparia dulcis* L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Chenopodium album* L., *Physalis heterophylla* Nees., *Enhydra fluctuans* Lour., *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link., *Echinochloa crusgalli* (L.) P.Beauv. were the most dominating weed species in the experimental field. No phytotoxic effect of herbicide was visually observed in the experimental plot. Based on the two years results, it was found that Panida® 33 EC showed highest weed control efficiency (83.84% and 85.54%) in 2023–24 and 2024–25 at 25 DAS. All other pre-emergence herbicides also control weed effectively than control and hand weeding. The highest grain yield (4.30 t ha⁻¹ and 4.34 t ha⁻¹) was recorded in Panida® 33 EC in 2023–24 and 2024–25 and the lowest grain yield (3.40 t ha⁻¹ and 3.32 t ha⁻¹) was recorded in Weedy check (Control) treatment in both the years. All other herbicides also gave statistically identical grain yield. The highest gross return (1,88,190 Tk ha⁻¹) and MBCR (2.34) was found in Panida® 33 EC and the lowest (1,46,775 Tk ha⁻¹ and 1.92) was found in Weedy check (Control). All other herbicides also provided higher MBCR than hand weeding.

Keywords BWMRI Gom 3, Pendimethalin, Weed control efficiency, Grain yield, MBCR